

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE CONFORMAL MAPPING OF THE VAITKEVICHIVS-VOLK FUNCTION AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH THE VORTEX DYNAMICS OF A THREE-CHAMBER SPHEROIDAL VORTEX

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Abstract

This work is devoted to the consideration of the behavior of conformal quasi-harmonics that characterize the behavior of vortex domains within the framework of the conformal mapping of the Vaitkevichius-Volk function. A conformal analysis of the automorphic function of this conformal mapping was carried out and the pattern of existence of the connectivity of the function with the core of the lemniscate strip was revealed. The mechanism of formation of isogonal potential and isothermal vortex fields of function (1) on a circle of a Riemannian two-sheet plane was studied. A new characteristic is given to the complex values of the divergence and shear of these fields.

Keywords: conformal mapping, vortex dynamics of matter, conformal geometry, Riemannian geometry, lemniscate geometry

1. Introduction

The difficulty of the problem was that the conformal mapping of the Lindemann function $f(\sqrt{R})$ had doubly periodicity [1-4], and it was necessary to find the optimal geometric solution corresponding to the laws of distribution of matter by potential. F.Lindemann (1882) solved this problem through a conformal mapping of the function $1/(z_1 - z)$ over the Lamé functions, which are obtained from the representation of the reciprocal of the distance between two focal points in space under the condition where the z-plane is understood as a system of confocal (confocal) ellipses. O.T. Volk (1925) performed the same task for an imaginary quantity [5]. When solving this fundamental problem of biperiodicity, the question arose: how will the conformal mapping function $f = \omega(\sqrt[3]{R})$ behave when the number n of the root and degree of the rational function is equal to 3.

2. Conformal mapping of the Vaitkevichius-Volk function

This problem of finding "quasi-harmonics" within a closed circle was brilliantly applied by O.T. Volk's student, mathematician Antanas Vaitkevichius (1931) in his remarkable work "About the conformal function $\omega = \sqrt[3]{\frac{z^3+1}{z^3-1}}$ mapping" [6].

Here the originality of the work lies in the fact that this function

$$\omega = \sqrt[3]{\frac{z^3+1}{z^3-1}} \quad (1)$$

is remarkable in that it has the same inverse function

$$z = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\omega^3+1}{\omega^3-1}} \quad (2)$$

A more detailed study of the properties of the conformal Vaitkevichius-Volk mapping within the frame-

work of an ellipsoidal vortex was carried out by the author Milyute in works [3, 4, 7], in which it was noted that the connection between the sheet lemniscate planes determines the connectivity of these planes [3, 7]. It is known that the Z plane has three layers ($n = 3$) and should be thought of as three-sheeted with the zero point as a turning point of the $(n - 1)$ th order, bypassing which you can get from one sheet to another without jumping. Each sector of the $\frac{2n\pi}{3}$ level corresponds to such a sheet.

Here there is a corresponding lemniscatic affinity of the 3rd ($n = 3$) order, which is always expressed by a function of the form

$$z = \sqrt[3]{\frac{a\omega^3+b}{c\omega^3-d}} \quad a, b, c, d = 1 \quad (3)$$

just as any circular relation can be replaced by a transformation through inverse radius vectors with respect to a certain circle, so the 3rd order lemniscate relation is reduced to an isothermal reflection with respect to a certain lemniscate with a zero point in the center:

$$z = \varepsilon + \sqrt[3]{\frac{\omega^3+1}{\omega^3-1}} \quad (4)$$

It was noted that the three-field lemniscate in the conformal image of the Vaitkevichius-Volk function (1) in inversion behaves like a three-field vortex, the arms of which have the property of turning over when moving from one sheet to another, and have a closed self-preservation property [3, 4, 7].

3. Automorphic function of the Vaitkevichius-Volk conformal map

To better understand the dynamics of lemniscate-conformal mappings for a circle, we first study in more detail the geometry of linear polymorphic functions (an extended version of Riemannian geometry), which have properties of functions inverse to automorphic functions. It is known that not only Fuchs functions

have the properties of automorphic functions, as noted by Poincaré [8-9], but also closed vortex domains that preserve autowave substantiality, self-preserving, as long as the closedness and conservation of the kern energy of the ellipsoidal vortex are preserved [10]. In our case, we will accept that the argument of automorphism is the quantity ω , which obeys the condition $z = \varphi(\omega)$. Here the ω -half-plane of the function $z = \varphi(\omega)$ (2) will be represented on a closed Riemannian plane over the plane having half p . Let the hexagon (Fig. 2 g) have vertices = 6, which are fixed points of elliptic or parabolic formulations, and let these points (pole and zero points) correspond to the points of Riemannian geometry located at the points $z_n = m_1, m_2, \dots, m_7, (m = 7)$. The angles of a polygon at the angles under consideration are equal

$$\left((m_1 - 1) \frac{2\pi}{3}, (m_2 - 1) \frac{2\pi}{3}, \dots, (m_7 - 1) \frac{2\pi}{3} \right),$$

where $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_7$ are whole numbers, $1 \leq m \leq 7$.

The composition (p, n) is called the “character of the automorphic group,” which describes the development of independent twisted autowaves at the vertex

points of the hexagon. We will assume that the new expression $(p, n; m_1, m_2, \dots, m_7)$ is being a signature of a Riemannian space with special two branches located at the vertices $n = 6$.

Let function (2) be the inverse of function (1), and we call function (2) a linear polymorphic function on the surface, because these replacements are such that, in a suitable way of cutting, the surface is a polygon of the main circle, as is the case in the theory of factual broken lines z , and general groups of the main circle appear in the linearly replaced area.

In this case, the comparison with the theory of elliptic functions is well known. Here we will adopt the new concept of a “periodic parallelogram”, curved in such a way as shown in Fig. 3 b in the form of a lemniscate strip. Namely, that the mapping of “parallel transport” of matter along one lemniscate strip follows from the study of conformal mappings of function (3) (see Fig. 2 a-c).

And this phenomenon is being an improvement on the problem of mapping Riemann's two-leaf geometry onto the surface of a lemniscate strip having simple connectivity.

Fig.. 1 Choreographic recording of field changes

Fig. 2 Spectral analysis of conformal mappings of the Vaitkevichius-Volk function.

It is the lemniscate strip that obviously solves the issue of “continuity” of the function within this framework, which was repeatedly emphasized in the Riemann problem geometry by Klein [11].

This means that we are dealing, on the one hand, with the individual signature (p, n) of the closed space of the conformal mapping of function (3), and from here we find a continuum of related automorphic structures - peculiar vortex domains $(p, n; m_1, m_2, \dots, m_{n+1})$ (as shown in fig. 2 and 1). It follows that each piecewise Riemannian surface at the vertices of the hexagon receives a circular polygon through two cuts. This is how

we go through the double branching of a piecewise independent region (along the separatrix line) according to Lindemann [1]. Thus, we come to the conclusion that a polygon with six vertices is an image of a (triple) cut two-leaf Riemannian geometry, which we can identify with the stripes of the lemniscate. Having formed a "group of elliptic modules":

$$(0, 6; m_1, m_2, \dots, m_7)$$

we get a function that represents a piece of a 3rd order surface:

$$x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - xyz + ux + vy + \omega z + J = 0 \quad (5)$$

where, for a two-dimensional surface (2nd order surface) from formula (5), taking $z = 0$, we obtain the following equation:

$$x^2 + y^2 + ux + vy + J = 0, \quad (6)$$

where the theory of polygons (triangular domains) represents a double triangle located in this area (see Fig. 4). Where each elementary triangle and the connecting bridge as a boundary can have interconnected relation-ships

$$\begin{cases} yz - 2x = u \\ zx - 2y = v \\ xy - 2z = \omega \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Thus we see that another triangle is created as a kind of result of the reflection of the first on one of its three sides.

The opposite continuum of algebraic structures includes all planes, drawn by four points $((m_1 - 1)\frac{2\pi}{3}, (m_2 - 1)\frac{2\pi}{3}, \dots, (m_4 - 1)\frac{2\pi}{3})$, which can lie at the vertices of a quadrilateral.

This continuum is invariant through all complex values of the double relation:

$$\lambda = -\frac{(m_1 - m_2)(m_3 - m_4)}{(m_1 - m_3)(m_4 - m_2)} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3. Representations of simply connectivity and biconnectivity according to Riemann and according to the rule of the lemniscate strip [3]

And from here the illustration of the plane of a double triangle can be studied, which can be clearly seen in Fig. 4 and 2. And formula (8) clearly reflects the property of the lemniscate strip.

First of all, we note that the edge of an elementary triangle runs straight along the entire real axis λ , and the angles of the triangle provide different positions $\lambda = 0, 1, \infty$. (here the role of infinity is played by rotation along the lemniscate strip).

It is safe to say that the double triangle and the λ -plane are clearly related to each other: on each plane covered by four points, there is a polymorphic function that maps the same function to the underlying polygon of a circle with a given signature $(p, n; m_1, m_2, \dots, m_{n+1})$, thus proving consistency and continuity for a number of other signatures of the

Fig. 4

manifold of one, two or three dimensions, we can construct an obvious crystallographic picture of the location of these vortex domains in two-dimensional or three-dimensional structural space, without resorting to complex mathematical calculations of elliptic functions in the conformal version.

3 Equipotential and vortex fields of the conformal mapping of the Vaitkevichius-Volk function

In this case, the movements of points of isogonal lines can be considered as plane problems with a fairly accurate approximation that obeys these laws in the algebra of a complex variable

$$div \omega = \omega_{\bar{z}} - \bar{\omega}_z \quad (9)$$

$$curl \omega = \frac{1}{i}(\omega_{\bar{z}} - \bar{\omega}_z), \quad (10)$$

where the complex quantity $\omega_{\bar{z}}$ is found from the formula:

$$\omega_{\bar{z}} = \frac{1}{2}(div \omega + i curl \omega) \quad (11)$$

From equation (11) it can be seen that the total motion of a point, consisting of the sum of radial motion and transverse torsion (shear) as a whole. And since there are two different vectors $\omega_{\bar{z}}$ and $\bar{\omega}_z$ at work here, located on different lemniscate planes, they create the “appearance of three-dimensional space.”

The advantage of the rational function as a function of the third root (1) is that it can connect the centers of three lemniscate strips so that the flow of matter on them passes unimpeded while

maintaining circulation (see Fig. 2.8 b from [3]) without resistance in them (the so-called sliding flows in

them), which is very important to keep in mind when calculating closed circulating flows.

Fig. 5: Vortex (a) and potential (b) fields.
Vortex trivalent $n1*n2 = 6 = 2*3$ [3, 4]

From Fig. 5 it is clear that the potential field of the conformal mapping (1) works only on three separate sheets in the conformal geometry. This suggests that the conformal geometry of the rational function of the third root (2) can be represented by zonal quasi-spherical functions of six (three real and three

imaginary) sectors on the Riemannian sphere (Fig. 4.6 from [3]). The circulation movement follows the polygon law in a flat version when performing the inversion (transverse rotation) of the lemniscate strip of the trihexaflexagon [2,4,5].

Fig. 6 Lines of motion of matter in a spheroidal vortex ($n = 3$) (three-chamber cavity of a circle) (top view)

The flow of matter in a three-chamber vortex is described by function (1), and from Figure 6 the main flow lines are clearly visible, ensuring the continuity of the function (1) [3,4].

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